

Homoaromaticity for undergraduate students : The basics and a bit more

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Abstract : As an extension of the important concept of aromaticity, the topics of homoaromaticity and homoconjugation have been rightly introduced in the undergraduate syllabus. Discussion of these topics hinges critically upon the introduction to the so called “no-bond, through space” overlap between orbitals which, in turn, may pose a serious intellectual barrier to young students unfamiliar with such alien concept of non-classical bonding. This paper attempts to dispel the possible confusions and offers a basic understanding of homoaromaticity through a treatment suitable for undergraduate students.

Introduction

Aromaticity is an important and popular concept in organic chemistry teaching, education and research. Cyclic delocalization of π -electrons may confer special stability and other peculiar properties in certain organic molecules, while the same can give rise to special instability in others. These compounds are classified as *aromatic* and *antiaromatic* respectively. In this connection the famous Hückel's rule is often taught in undergraduate classes to identify aromatic or antiaromatic compound. A monocyclic conjugated polyene having $(4n+2)$ π -electrons, where 'n' being an integer, delocalized over the ring is a typical aromatic molecule, while such delocalization of $4n$ π -electrons endows antiaromatic character. Cyclic polyenes lacking such uninterrupted conjugation or the required number of π -electrons are often dubbed *nonaromatic*. However, beyond these simplistic classifications there are subtler aspects of aromatic behaviour. Some mole-

cules exhibit aromatic-like character even though the formal cyclic overlap of p -orbitals is absent, which preclude their classification as aromatic systems following the Hückel's rule. This curious phenomenon was described as *homoaromaticity*. A typical example of such a homoaromatic system is the homotropylium ion (the higher homologue of the aromatic tropylium ion), where 6 π -electrons (a $4n+2$ number) are delocalised over seven carbon centres bypassing the eighth carbon, a saturated methylene unit. There are evidences indicative of considerable interaction between two carbons which *do not* share any formal chemical bond between them. The orbital overlap of two π -systems separated by a non-conjugating group, such as CH_2 and concomitant sustenance (albeit to a limited degree) of the electron delocalization over multi-atomic distances is known as *homoconjugation*. The concept of homoaromaticity has drawn attention because of such unusual no-bond orbital overlap and over the years a large volume of experimental and theoretical work has been directed towards understanding the nature of bonding and other aspects of these molecules. The reason to take up this much important but unfamiliar topic to undergraduate student community is its varied application even in the simpler molecules. Yet, such an endeavour is bound to meet with intellectual challenges and barriers as the concept of no-bond overlap is somehow contrary to the students' intuition and understanding of formal chemical bond. That is probably why most undergraduate textbooks tend to gloss over this less familiar concept, hardly providing any deeper insight. The current paper attempts to resolve this issue and offers a basic understanding of homoaromaticity through a treatment which we hope is suitable for young chemists.

The concept of aromaticity and Hückel's rule :

As mentioned earlier, the cyclic, unsaturated, fully conjugated polyene molecules can be classified as aromatic or antiaromatic on the basis of the stability of these with a certain number of π -electron in comparison to their acyclic counterparts. If they are more stable than their acyclic partners then they are called aromatic, e.g. benzene. On the other hand if they are less stable than their acyclic partners they are called antiaromatic, e.g. cyclobutadiene (CBD). Though another class of cyclic unsaturated poly-

enes do not belong to the aforementioned classification because of their non-planar nature and subsequent loss of cyclic overlap and these are called nonaromatic compounds, e.g. cyclooctatetraene (COT). These compounds exhibit comparable stability corresponding to their acyclic counterparts.

Thus, aromaticity may be defined as the stabilization of certain cyclic conjugated molecules due to the presence of filled-shell electronic configuration, e.g. benzene. In line of this, Erich Hückel postulated that monocarbocyclic, fully conjugated, planar molecules containing $(4n + 2)$ π -electrons where n is any integer including zero, are aromatic. For benzene, ' n ' is 1. Characteristics of aromatic molecules may be given in the following way – planar cyclic delocalized π -electron systems and are typified by the following ground state properties : (a) **more stable** than their corresponding acyclic analogs by an energy called the 'resonance energy' which is considered as an ground state stability of a molecule obtained as a result of linear combination of atomic orbitals, (b) with bond lengths intermediate between those of typical single and double bonds and (c) with a **π -electron ring current** induced by an external magnetic field, leading to increased diamagnetic susceptibility and typical diatropic [lowfield] chemical shifts of exocyclic protons in ^1H NMR spectra. An additional characteristic very frequently used by organic chemists, is that : (d) aromatic compounds generally undergo **substitution** reactions (the so-called aromatic substitution) more easily than addition. Spectroscopically aromatic compounds show higher energy ultraviolet/visible spectral bands and a more symmetrical structure for their IR spectra.

Cyclic overlap of p-orbitals in benzene

Diamagnetic ring current induced by closed loop of p-electrons
In presence of uniform external magnetic field (B_0)

The concept of aromaticity is equally applicable in case of charged rings; cyclopropenyl cation (2π -electrons), cyclopentatrienyl anion (6π -electrons) and cycloheptatrienyl cation (tropylium ion, 6π -electrons) are all examples of stabilized aromatic systems.

Antiaromatic and nonaromatic compounds :

Antiaromatic molecules are cyclic systems containing alternating single and double bonds, where the π -electron energy of the cyclic molecule is higher than that of its open-chain counterpart. Therefore antiaromatic compounds are unstable and highly reactive, often distorting themselves out of

planarity to resolve this instability. As per the IUPAC criteria antiaromatic molecules must have $4n$ π -electrons where n is any integer. The molecule must be cyclic having a conjugated π -electron system and it must be planar¹. Cyclobutadiene (CBD) is a prime candidate for such behavior and to avoid antiaromatic destabilization the ground state geometry of CBD is rectangular, not planar, a result of a Jahn-Teller distortion.

Two diastereoisomeric forms of rectangular 1,2-dideuterocyclobuta-1,3-diene
Distortion from square planar geometry is a consequence of antiaromatic conjugation within the closed loop of 4 π -electrons².

Cyclooctatetraene (COT), on the other hand, has 8 π -electrons ($4n$, $n = 2$), but it behaves like an unconjugated tetraene with four isolated single and double bonds. It escapes planarity and assumes tub-shape to avoid antiaromatic destabilization. This is a typical nonaromatic behaviour.

COT dication and dianion are aromatic as they satisfy the criteria for being an aromatic compounds/species. The structures of the said dication and dianion derived from COT are planar.

The dianion K-salt's crystal structure has shown 'aromatic' bond lengths for C-C bond with 1.41 Å. The dication has proton and carbon-NMR spectral signatures of a diamagnetic species, a characteristic of aromatic compounds. Chemical shifts are indicative of aromatic anisotropy in the eight membered ring³.

But, what happens if we obtain a monocation from COT⁴?

C_8H_9^+ – the peculiar monocation from COT is of particular interest :

The monocation has an eight membered ring, with one sp^3 -hybridized carbon atom, so it is supposed to behave like a **nonaromatic** compound, as per Hückel's $(4n+2)$ π -electron rule (because of formal discontinuity in conjugation). However the ^1H NMR spectra tells a very different story. The ^1H NMR data for the monocation is : δ 8.5 (5H, m), H-2, H-3, H-4, H-5, H-6 (similar to that of the tropylium ion, clearly an aromatic species); δ 6.6 (2H, m), H-1, H-7; δ 5.2 (1H, m), H-8 (exo); δ -0.6 (1H, m), H-8 (endo)⁴. The cation also shows almost perfect C-C bond equalization in the seven membered ring, strong stabilization (RE : 22.8 kcal mol⁻¹) by the π -overlap, and a short C-1-C-7 distance (~ 2 Å)⁵. All these facts indicate that

there is an interaction between C-1 and C-7 atoms, even though they are not formally bonded, merely close to each other in space.

What is homoaromaticity?

This monocation was named as Homotropylium ion by **Saul Winstein of UCLA (1959)** and was identified as a “**Homoaromatic**” species. The term “Homoaromaticity” was introduced to describe interrupted cyclic delocalization of π -electrons due to the presence of one or more sp^3 hybridized atoms. Literally it means *homologous aromaticity*. Thus homoaromatic species result from the cyclic delocalization of $(4n+2)$ π -electrons in systems where the aromatic pericycle is interrupted by one or more methylene groups, e.g. the monocation derived from COT.

The homotropylium ion can be *conceptually* derived from the parent aromatic system, the tropylium cation, by inserting one methylene group (C-8) between any two adjacent carbons.

The orbital interaction between two non-adjacent p-centres (C-1, C-7) is thought to be maintained in spite of interposition of the methylene group between them. However, this interaction is considerably less than that of a formal chemical bond.

Criteria for Homoaromaticity can be summed up as : (i) the system must possess one or more *homoconjugative* interactions (either through bond, or through space), (ii) electron delocalization in the closed cyclic system should be characterized by (a) effective overlap between the π -orbitals of the cyclic system, (b) bond orders approaching that of the π -system, (c) in case of charged molecules delocalization of charge throughout the cyclic system, (d) relatively large bond equalization with bond lengths intermediate of double and single bonds, (iii) the number of π -electrons delocalized over the cyclic system should be $(4n+2)$, (iv) homoaromaticity should lead to a stabilizing resonance energy of $> 2 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, (v) the system should possess exceptional magnetic properties such as : (a) significant equalization of ^{13}C chemical shifts in the cyclic system, (b) a large chemical shift difference between *endo* and *exo* protons attached to the methylene carbon located above the cyclic conjugated system (C-8 in case of Homotropylium ion, $\Delta\delta 5.8 \text{ ppm}^6$). Let us now take a deeper look at homoaromaticity in the light of *homoconjugative interactions*.

What is homoconjugation?

Homoconjugation depicts itself the orbital overlap of two π -systems, separated by a non-conjugating group, such as a methylene unit. 1,4-Pentadiene has a through space interaction between C-2 and C-4. In case of methylenecyclopropane there is "through-bond" homoconjugation.

Homoaromaticity for undergraduate students :

Cyclic homoconjugation involving $(4n+2)$ π -electrons endows homotropylium ion with aromatic properties. C-1 and C-7 share a “through-space/no bond” homoconjugative interaction. This “no-bond” homoconjugative interaction is also responsible for the aromatic behaviour of homocyclopropenium/cyclobutenyl ion. Homoaromatic character of cyclobutenyl ion is shown by nearly equal charge distribution over C-1, C-2, and C-3, short C-1–C-3 bond distance (1.74 \AA)⁷.

Transannular homoconjugative interactions can lead to another type of Homoaromaticity.

In these bridged [10]annulenes which undergo $S_{\text{E}}\text{Ar}$ and show diatropic nature, there is significant transannular homoconjugation. This perturbs the aromatic stabilization of the 10π -electrons system although no straightforward interruption in conjugation exists. The molecule should more appropriately be called homonaphthalene. The no-bond homoconjugative interaction between C-1 and C-6 affects the conjugation between C-2 and C-7 to such an extent that the protodesilylation reaction at C-2 is almost insensitive to electronic effects of substituents at C-7⁸. Other examples include homoazulene and homoanthracene :

Revisiting our homotropylium ion we can therefore consider it as a higher homologue of tropylium ion where the aromatic characters have been modified by insertion of a homoconjugative linkage between two adjacent carbons.

Another curious observation : what happens if we protonate (C)?

The “less stable” secondary carbocation is actually bishomoaromatic, maintaining a cyclic homoconjugation with 6-electrons. The homoconjugative interactions are between C-1, C-3 and C-7, C-9⁹.

Homoaromaticity for undergraduate students :

The number of interrupting methylene can be even more than two : The trishomoaromatics acetolysis of *cis*-3-bicyclo[3.1.0]hexyl tosylate is much faster than the corresponding *trans* isomer. Anchimeric assistance of C-1–C-5 single bond is believed to be responsible for this rate enhancement. The intermediate cation is a trishomoaromatic system, where 2 electrons are delocalized over 3 centres and the cyclic conjugation is interrupted by alternating methylene groups. The trishomocyclopropenyl cation is a homoaromatic species having three homoconjugations.

Evidences supporting the facts are (i) 1,3-deuterated substance shows scrambling of label over C-3, C-1, and C-5¹⁰, (ii) homoconjugative distances are all equal, C-1–C-3, C-3–C-5 and C-5–C-1 (1.82 Å)¹¹, (iii) positive charge is evenly distributed over C-1, C-3 and C-5¹². Substitution of C-6 in the cation with O and NH decreases the homoaromaticity, while BH substitution promotes it. Clearly the electronic nature of the substituents attenuates such homoconjugation¹¹.

Anionic homoaromaticity is also being debated...

Bicyclo[3.2.1]octadienyl anion is a proposed anionic homoaromatic system. Computational studies provide evidence both in favour¹² and against¹³ of such an assignment and the issue is yet to be resolved. X-Ray crystal structure of the anion with Li⁺ counterion is available and correlates well with these calculations.

Comparison of pK_a values of the following two carbon acids is illustrative :

Anion “D” is at least 12.2 kcal mol⁻¹ more stable than anion “E”. The difference of stability reflects anionic bishomoaromatic stabilization of “D”

over “E”¹⁴. The bishomocyclopentadienyl character of anion “D” is also indicated by existing diatropic ring current, evident from δ 2.3 ppm upfield shift of C-6 and C-7 protons in the ¹H NMR spectrum in comparison to its conjugate acid¹⁵. Several other examples of anionic homoaromaticity exist in heterocyclic compounds.

Like antiaromaticity, is there antihomoaromaticity?

Protonated 1,6-methano[10]annulene is a potential antihomoaromatic species. It is a 8 π -electron system and to minimize such destabilization it avoids C-1, C-3 homoconjugation. The C-1–C-6 interaction is also compromised¹⁶.

Another observation includes solvolysis of “F” is 235 times faster than “H”. This difference in rate is attributed to the difference of stabilities of two intermediate carbocations (G and I), one being allylic and the other an antihomoaromatic¹⁷. Recent calculations¹⁸ have shown “G” to be more stable than “I” by 6.07 kcal mol⁻¹.

The antihomoaromatic species “J” has been observed as a static cation in superacid media at low temperature. This undergoes fast rearrangement to “K” at $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to get rid of the destabilizing homoconjugative interactions¹⁹.

Conclusions

Homoaromaticity/homoantiaromaticity are concepts worth attention because they conceive of the unusual no-overlap interaction between non-adjacent orbitals, namely the homoconjugation. This may confer the system with unexpected stability and other properties typical of aromatic compounds, although the cyclic conjugation of p-orbitals is formally interrupted here. Exciting new structures and models of bonding has already been proposed, and new ideas are coming up as well. It also goes to show the finer aspects of the age-old concept of aromaticity and the limitation of Hückel’s theory which appears to be a too simplistic description of a varied and vast array of “unusual” molecules. In fact, through this seemingly aberrational concept of no-bond overlap the student is presented with a whole new vista of chemical bonding where s/he must understand that as a learner s/he is being presented with generalizations to which there are many exceptions, as is the wont of a growing and expanding subject such as chemistry.

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